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Article in *Air Quality Atmosphere & Health* · March 2025

DOI: 10.1007/s11869-025-01710-x

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An Accurate Two-Stage Deep Machine Learning Aided Air Quality Estimation Based on Multiple Gases from Aerial Images

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Abstract

Currently, industry-related environmental factors negatively affect human health. The Air Quality Index (AQI), a measurement of air pollution, is worsening and affecting our daily life. Increasing air pollution, concerns about climate change, evolving technologies, and environmental research estimate air quality as increasingly important. Air pollution management has become crucial, and environmental monitoring conditions and air quality in daily life are necessary. The latest research on AQI does not focus on aerial images or specific pollutants. Additionally, avoid tackling the issue of having a high level of some

specific weather elements, such as temperature and humidity. In the proposed research, we tackle the issues mentioned above by splitting our investigation into two phases. Thus, in this paper, an image-based high-accuracy air quality monitoring system is realised in two stages. In the first stage of our examination, popular deep machine learning prediction algorithms, including Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Convolution Neural Networks (CNN), CNN-Long Short Term Memory (CNN-LSTM), and MobileNetv2 networks, for the assignment into different categories of the AQI, targeting the AQI prediction with the utilisation of aerial images. Next, the second stage utilises ANN, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), LSTM, and RNN-B-LSTM popular deep machine learning techniques to develop a regression prediction system trained with the features and the resulting classification of air quality results from the highest accuracy approach of the first stage (which is the ANN approach with 99.14% accuracy). To tackle the issue of overfitting/underfitting, the oversampling technique (SMOTE) is used. The proposed method considers the contribution of each significant pollutant gas (i.e., PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, NH₃, SO₂, O₃) to the overall air quality index (AQI). The weather elements such as temperature and humidity impact air quality; they are also considered in our examination, resulting in a more accurate forecast. In addition, a comparison study is performed to identify the best model architecture for the proposed prediction system. Finally, the results show that the first stage of image classification should be executed with ANN (99.14 % accuracy), which is a highly accurate approach, and the second stage should be executed with the RNN-B-LSTM approach, again because of its high accuracy (98.73 % accuracy).

Keywords: Air Quality Estimation, Classification, Regression, RNN, RNN-B-LSTM, CNN, CNN-LSTM, MobileNetv2, Prediction, ANN, LSTM, Image Classification, Image Processing, Digital Signal Processing

1 Introduction

Unfortunately, our existence on Earth is in danger due to releasing of harmful suspended particulates into the atmosphere; air pollution has been a significant cause for concern. It causes approximately 7 million deaths worldwide and is considered one of the world's most important environmental health threats ([Du et al., 2021](#); [Organization, 2023](#)).

In India, for instance, air pollution is pervasive, and Delhi is among the urban areas with the most toxic air in the world. It causes and exacerbates various respiratory and cardiac diseases, including asthma, cancer, and other pulmonary conditions. People are exposed to toxic, thick smog, significantly reducing their life expectancy. Thus, pollution monitoring is becoming essential, and the air quality index (AQI) has become a necessary metric for measuring pollution levels. Innovations and research to reduce and analyse air pollution have gained prominence recently. [Additionally, in recent years, Delhi, the bustling capital city of India, has emerged as an epitome of urban air pollution challenges. Characterized by its dense population, significant industrial activities, and heavy vehicular traffic, Delhi presents a complex and pressing](#)

case for studying air quality issues. Our research primarily focuses on this metropolis, leveraging its diverse environmental conditions as a foundation for developing and testing advanced machine learning models. The high levels of pollutants in Delhi's atmosphere not only pose severe health risks but also offer a unique opportunity to understand the intricacies of urban pollution. This study employs the Air Quality Index (AQI) as a key metric, integrating it with cutting-edge AI techniques to provide deeper insights into the patterns and predictors of air pollution in Delhi. By concentrating on this city, we aim to uncover valuable data-driven solutions that address the urgent need for effective air quality management in heavily polluted urban environments. Air quality estimation will be effective in reducing the health risk it poses (Agency, 2021). Various machine learning techniques have been proposed to estimate the Air Quality Index (AQI) over the years. It is possible to predict the AQI by categorising it into its severity category or estimating the actual index values. Based on numerical data collected from weather monitoring stations, prediction algorithms such as linear regression, decision tree, random forest, artificial neural network, and support vector machine were used to predict the AQI. With the growing popularity and convenience of portable cameras and affordable smartphones, it is necessary to estimate PM2.5 directly from photographs. The originality/novelty of this research is that it aims to classify and predict the air quality index using aerial images (from non-HDR, Delhi-collected skyscape images from five distinct locations) by identifying different and multiple gasses (more than three) in a two-stage Deep Machine Learning Manner.

More precisely, unlike existing AQI prediction systems that rely solely on particulate matter, we consider all the major pollutants, including PM2.5, PM10, NO_x, SO₂, CO, NH₃, and Ozone, as well as temperature and humidity. Additionally, in the first stage of our examination, we use well-known machine learning classification ML algorithms, such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Convolution Neural Networks (CNN), Convolution neural network-Long Short-Term Memory Neural Networks (CNN-LSTM), and MobileNetv2 networks, to classify the AQI into different categories using aerial images (Albawi et al., 2017; Chauhan et al., 2018; Li et al., 2021; Islam et al., 2020; Narula and Vaegae, 2022; Padalia et al., 2022; Golcuk et al., 2023; Hu and Guo, 2021; Nagrath et al., 2021; Xiang et al.). As a result, the ANN achieved the highest accuracy among the others (99.14 %). Then, after the classification, as a second task, we use the resulting classification results of the AQI class, separated by day, along with utilised popular deep machine learning prediction algorithms, such as ANN, Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), LSTM, and Recurrent Neural Network-Bidirectional-Long Short-Term Memory Neural Networks (RNN-B-LSTM) to predict the exact value of AQI for the next timestamp (day) (Sherstinsky, 2020; Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1996, 1997; Graves et al., 2008; Yu et al., 2019; Graves and Schmidhuber, 2005; Gers et al., 2002; Reddy and Delen, 2018). More specifically, by using the first stage classification results and utilising the selected features as a training set through the time perspective (use the timestamp/day of each classification) and with the additional feature of the actual AQI index measured and calculated by hand and with the utilisation of measurement devices for the specific day of the classification results, the RNN-B-LSTM over all the other investigated approaches achieved the highest accuracy (98.73%). Finally, as shown above, our approach is an accurate

two-stage Deep ML implementation approach. The key contributions of this paper are summarised below:

- Overall, we estimate the existence and quantity of the following multiple gases: PM2.5, PM10, NO_x, NH₃, SO₂ and O₃ with the use of aerial images and AI/ML for the calculation/prediction of the AQI over the years.
- We redefine the AQI estimation conditions to the minimum three pollutants that exist from the list of the investigated pollutants (PM2.5, PM10, NO_x, NH₃, SO₂, O₃), out of which one is PM2.5 or PM10.
- We are the only method that employs a two-stage algorithm that utilises Deep Learning Machine Learning models in both stages.
- In the first stage, we utilise ML approaches (MobileNetV2 architecture, CNN, CNN-LSTM and ANN) for doing image classification targeting the categorisation and labelling of specific groups of pixels or vectors within an image according to specific feature extraction rules from the images in order to estimate the existence and the quantity of the gases mentioned above.
- We compare MobileNetV2, CNN, CNN-LSTM and ANN approaches to classifying the aerial images targeting the prediction of the air quality index. The classification images are separated into classes of values (Good:0-50, Satisfactory:51-100, Moderate:101-200, Poor:201-300, Very Poor:301-400, Severe:>401). The results from the classification examination show that the ANN-based classification of the existing images with SMOTE is proposed as the most accurate approach, with 99.14% accuracy.
- In the second stage, we utilise ML approaches (ANN, RNN, LSTM, and RNN-B-LSTM) for making predictions with the Use of regression in order to calculate/predict basically the Air Quality Index (AQI).
- We utilise and compare the ANN, RNN, LSTM, and RNN-B-LSTM approaches in terms of prediction accuracy of AQI, with the utilisation of the classification results gathered from the best classification technique that achieved the highest accuracy (ANN with 99.14%) in the first stage. The results show that the RNN-B-LSTM is the most appropriate approach for the second stage/round of investigation, which achieves a prediction of the following timestamp (in our case, a day) with 98,73%.
- An overall prediction accuracy of 98,73% is achieved with the proposed model (with SMOTE) by firstly using the ANN with SMOTE and by breaking the first stage classification of AQI into classes of values (Good:0-50, Satisfactory:51-100, Moderate:101-200, Poor:201-300, Very Poor:301-400, Severe:>401) than the exact value and secondly, by predicting the nearest value to the actual value in the second stage with the use of RNN-B-LSTM.

The remaining structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2 provides context for understanding the research and methodologies surrounding image-based air quality index prediction with a literature review related to the ML estimation of AQI. Section 3 provides the methodology used in this paper and describes the concept of the air quality index, the parameters/features involved, and the algorithms used for classification (first stage) and prediction (second stage). Section 4 shows the dataset that is used in the investigation along with the performance improvement techniques

used, such as the synthetic minority oversampling technique (SMOTE), the features extraction technique used, how the first stage models are trained for the classification, how the second stage models are trained for the prediction and the validation techniques used, such as the Cross-Validation. Section 5 describes the metrics used for both stages and the experimental outcomes obtained from the implementation stages. Section 6 concludes the paper and proposes future work.

2 Related work

The literature review of the related work to our examination can be broadly categorised into pollutant data analysis, image-dependent properties for air quality analysis, and machine learning-based air quality analysis. As an overall conclusion, we can indicate that the AQI-related literature does not emphasise aerial pictures or particular contaminants. In addition, they do not address the issue of excessive levels of specific meteorological components, such as temperature and humidity.

2.1 Pollutant data analysis

It is essential to comprehend the impact of various pollutants on the air quality index value and the representation of air pollutant data. Authors in (Mahajan et al., 2021) proposed methods to identify contaminants that significantly impact a region's AQI and also attempted to establish the trend and patterns of the identified pollutant. Examining the AQI levels across the nation provided insight into the seasonal and monthly variations in air quality. It was discovered that particulate matter (PM10 and PM2.5) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) had the highest correlation with AQI values. The trends of various pollutants with AQI were analysed to determine the significant pollutants. The results will help decision-makers devise counterstrategies well in advance to reduce the harmful effects of the primary pollutant, thereby improving air quality and reducing pollution.

Using real-time sensors and techniques such as the Fuzzy-C means, authors in (Madan et al., 2020) determined that the primary gaseous pollutants were Carbon dioxide, Carbon monoxide, and Ozone. The correlation between the AQI and particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10) and NO₂ is the strongest. Additionally, weather conditions such as temperature and humidity impacted air quality. Neural networks and boosting models use meteorological data such as temperature, wind speed, and humidity to predict the pollutant level accurately. According to authors in (Mahajan et al., 2021), low temperatures and high humidity act as a catalyst for the deterioration of air quality.

In (Grace et al., 2020), authors analysed and visualised real-time sensor data for six critical air pollutants, namely Ozone (O₃), Particulate Matter (PM2.5), Carbon Monoxide (CO), Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂), and Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂), and observed the overall air quality. To process the sensor data on polluted air, fuzzy c-Means clustering was employed.

In (Suman, 2021), authors proposed an air quality depreciation index that measures the deterioration of air quality on an environmental quality scale, considering the potential ability of pollutants to affect health and biophysical characteristics.

Authors in (Jumaah et al., 2019) developed an AQI prediction algorithm based on the analysis outcomes of meteorological parameters collected using an inverse distance weighted geostatistical technique, utilising a geographic information system (GIS) spatial statistical analysis method.

2.2 Image-dependent properties for air quality analysis

Numerous image characteristics and properties were used to predict AQI values. Authors in (Zhang and Dick, 2019) demonstrated the estimation of major pollutants such as PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, and NO₂ that can be performed concurrently using colour-dependent image characteristics such as scattering and absorption. In addition, the spatial properties of light attenuation within images were used in conjunction with position-dependent and colour-dependent properties, such as scattering and absorption, to improve prediction accuracy. This was accomplished by analysing the differences between various pollutants' scattering and absorption spectra. In (Chinu and Chhabra, 2014), the authors compared image edge detection techniques based on parameters such as edge type, localisation, nature, cost, and function. Adaptive parameters were used to implement the canny edge detection technique. It was determined that this technique with the adaptive parameters outperformed other operators in almost all conditions, albeit with its expensive execution time. This research shows how complex the investigation problem is, and it helped us to do the feature extraction on the images and classify them in the AQI class.

2.3 Machine learning-based air quality analysis

In the literature, several works demonstrated how The AQI value could be estimated using machine learning (ML)-based methods. According to (Madan et al., 2020), a neural network with an accuracy of 90% was found to be superior to other algorithms. However, the number of monitoring stations still needs to be increased for fine-grained air pollution monitoring.

Authors in (Chen et al., 2016) proposed a back propagation neural network (BPNN) model to estimate AQI values. Digital camera-captured images were extracted for their distinct edge and brightness characteristics. The extracted feature vectors were then fed to the trained BPNN model to obtain the AQI value. To construct the PM_{2.5} prediction model,

In (Yang and Chen, 2017), the authors proposed a robust linear regression algorithm. The predicted PM_{2.5} values and regression method are used to calculate the AQI, and the effect of relative humidity on estimating PM_{2.5} concentration has been identified.

Authors in (Chakma et al., 2017), proposed a method for estimating particulate matter with diameters less than 2.5 micrometres (PM 2.5). Two transfer learning methods, CNN fine-tuning and a random forest decision tree based on features fed into

a CNN network, was demonstrated to classify images into three PM2.5 concentration-based classes. The experimental results showed that the proposed PM2.5 concentration estimation method is valid. The proposed method employs a deep convolutional neural network to categorise natural images based on their PM2.5 concentrations. The model was evaluated using 591 Beijing-captured images accompanied by their corresponding PM2.5 concentrations.

In (Bo et al., 2018), the authors correlated images and weather data such as humidity and wind speed to estimate PM2.5 indices of outdoor images using deep learning and support vector regression (SVR) techniques and then used a convolutional neural network to predict the PM2.5 index based on the data image. The images are first fed to a ResNet model, which generates predicted PM2.5 indices. An SVR model then combines the ResNet output with two closely related meteorological variables, humidity, and wind speed, to generate a final PM2.5 estimation. Finally, the PM2.5 value predicted by CNN and weather characteristics were combined to produce the final PM2.5 index estimation.

Authors in (Rijal et al., 2018) proposed estimating PM2.5 concentrations by combining the PM2.5 predictions generated by three convolutional neural networks (VGG-16, Inception-v3, and ResNet50) with a feedforward neural network-based ensemble of deep neural networks-based regression. 1460 images of PM2.5 were used to evaluate the performance of the system. Using air quality datasets from Shijiazhuang City, China.

In (Wang et al., 2022), the investigation proposed an AQI prediction algorithm based on CNN and an improved long short-term memory (ILSTM) algorithm. The authors demonstrated the superiority of the proposed algorithm by comparing it with eight prediction models: SVR, RFR, MLP, GRU, LSTM, ILSTM, CNN-GRU, and CNN-LSTM.

In (Chen et al., 2020), authors proposed an hourly AQI prediction. The model employs a deep recurrent neural network based on the gated recurrent unit (GRU-BPNN) to obtain the final predicted value, which is then classified to determine the corresponding AQI level.

3 Methodology

This section demonstrates the adopted methodology in predicting the AQI. Firstly, we describe what the Air Quality Index (AQI) is. Then we show what Machine Learning (ML) techniques we will utilise for the classification of the aerial images according to the pollution factors. Finally, the prediction ML techniques that we will use and compare for the estimation of the AQI are shown. These approaches are trained based on the data set created from the classification and the feature extraction shown in Section 4.2.

3.1 Air quality index

The environmental protection agency (EPA) in the United States developed the AQI to measure the levels of air pollution (Board). The AQI is also used to help the public to understand air pollution. Citizens need to be aware of the daily levels of

air pollution due to its hazardous effects on health. The AQI combines the weighted values of various air pollutants into a single value. The primary purpose of AQI is to provide rapid results with the given pollutant levels.

3.1.1 AQI estimation

To calculate the AQI, the following conditions must be satisfied (Board):

1. At Least one value between PM2.5 and PM10 should be present.
2. At least three values amongst SO₂, NO₂, NH₃, CO, and O₃ must be present.

However, in our approach, we redefine the AQI estimation conditions to the minimum three pollutants that exist (SO₂, NO₂, NH₃, CO, O₃, PM2.5, PM10), out of which one is PM. The pollutant concentrations were then converted to a sub-index, bringing them all to a comparable measurement scale. The final AQI is the sub-index with the highest value. Figure.1 depicts a graphical representation of AQI calculation.

Fig. 1 Calculation of AQI

After calculating the AQI, the values were classified into the various buckets/classes shown in Table 1 and appended to the existing data frame before being exported.

Note that for the temperature and humidity, our investigation shows a direct dependency on the concentration of the air pollutants and both climate characteristics. When the temperature drops, the warm air layer functions as a lid, trapping cold air at the surface. This explains the negative link between temperature and particle pollution by preventing particulate pollution from escaping. Humidity refers to the amount of airborne moisture. The strong positive association between humidity and particle pollutants explains why high humidity levels have a high potential to trap pollutants, hence increasing the concentration of pollutants. This is why our approach of measuring the intensity of each pollutant air indirectly does not need to investigate the temperature and humidity.

Table 1 AQI buckets/classes and its impact on human health.

AQI range	AQI bucket/class	Impact on human health
0-50	Good	Minimal Impact.
51-100	Satisfactory	Minor breathing discomfort to sensitive people.
101-200	Moderate	Leads to breathing difficulty to people with pulmonary and cardiac ailments and older adults.
201-300	Poor	Causes difficulty in breathing to people on prolonged exposure.
301-400	Very Poor	Leads to respiratory diseases to people on prolonged exposure.
>401	Severe	Causes respiratory problems even to healthy people.

3.2 First Stage: Classification of Images to Classes of AQI

Image classification is the process of labelling or categorising an entire image. Images should only include a single class. Classification models receive an image as input and estimate the class type to which the image belongs. The categorisation of images entails the application of categorising and labelling groups of pixels or vectors inside an image based on predetermined rules. One or more spectral or textural characterisations may be applied as a classification law. In this Section, we classify each image based on the gasses identified to a specific class of AQI. Additionally, this section provides a description of the approaches used for the first classification stage. These are the: i) CNN; ii) MobileNetV2; iii) CNN-LSTM; and iv) ANN (it is also used in the regression stage);

Supervised image classification methods employ previously classified reference samples to train the classifier, which is then used to classify unknown data. Therefore, supervised classification is the process of visually selecting training data samples within an image and assigning them to predetermined categories. This is performed to apply statistical measurements to the entire image.

More specifically, 'Maximum likelihood' and 'minimum distance' are two of the most popular methods for classifying the overall image using training data. Maximum likelihood classification employs the data's statistical properties, first analysing the standard deviation and mean values of the image's textural and spectral indices. Later, the likelihood of each pixel belonging to distinct classes is calculated using a normal distribution for each pixel (at each pixel class). In addition, a few traditional statistical methods and probabilistic relationships are employed. Eventually, pixels are assigned to the class of features with the highest probability.

3.2.1 Convolution neural network

A Convolution neural network or ConvNet (CNN) is a type of neural network that specialises in processing data with a grid-like topology, such as an image. Deep convolutional neural networks are one type of deep neural network that can recognise and classify specific image features and is widely used for analysing visual images. CNN's

primary advantage is detecting important features automatically and without human intervention, (Liu et al., 2022; Albawi et al., 2017).

Typically, a CNN has three layers: the convolution layer, the pooling layer, and the fully connected layer. The CNN’s convolution layer carries most of the network’s computational load. This layer performs a dot product between two matrices, one of which is the kernel with a set of learnable parameters and the other being the restricted portion of the receptive field. The size of the kernel matrix is less than that of the receptive image field. During a forward pass, the kernel slides across the height and width of the image to generate the activation map, a two-dimensional representation of the image. If the size of the input is $W \times W \times D$, the kernel has a spatial size of F and a sliding size of S , and the amount of padding is P , then the output size can be calculated as follows:

$$W_{out} = \frac{W - F + 2P}{S} + 1 \quad (1)$$

This will produce a volume with the dimensions $W_{out} \times W_{out} \times D_{out}$, where D_{out} is the number of kernels. The primary objective of the convolution operation is to exploit sparse interaction, parameter sharing, and translation equivalence in images.

The second layer of the CNN, the pooling layer, replaces the network output at specific locations with a statistic (maximum or minimum) derived from nearby outputs. This helps reduce the spatial size of the representation, thereby reducing the computation and weighting requirements. If the size of the activation map is $W \times W \times D$, then the pooling kernel has a spatial size of F , and the stride is S , then the following formula can be used to determine the output volume size as follows:

$$W_{out} = \frac{W - F}{S} + 1 \quad (2)$$

Max pooling, a type of pooling operation, selects the maximum element from a neighbourhood after convolution.

The final layer is the fully connected (FC) layer, where all neurons in the preceding and succeeding layers are interconnected. The FC layer facilitates the mapping between the input and output representations. Figure 2 depicts the overall architecture of the CNN model that was used for training.

Fig. 2 CNN Architecture.

In the CCN, the utilised Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function is monotonically increasing and is given by Eq. 3:

$$f(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (3)$$

Due to the nature of its derivative, it aids in solving the problem of vanishing gradients. A softmax activation function was used at the output layer because it represents the probability that an input belongs to each class. The softmax function is given by,

$$s(x) = \frac{e^{x_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^n e^{x_j}} \quad (4)$$

The dropout layers are used in training the CNNs because they prevent overfitting on the training data. If they aren't present, the first batch of training samples influences the learning disproportionately.

3.2.2 MobileNetV2 Architecture

The MobileNetV2 is a type of CNN. In the rest of the paragraph, we will explain why the community widely uses it. It is used because training a neural network model from scratch requires a large quantity of data. Thus, a pre-trained model is useful when data is scarce. Transfer learning is applying a previously trained model to optimise it for a new task. The knowledge gained from a previous assignment can be applied to a new assignment to improve prediction. The model is utilised by adjusting and modifying specific parameters to suit our needs.

Google's MobileNetv2 is one of these pre-trained models, which can function as an efficient feature extractor. There are two types of network blocks. A block with residual stride one and another block with residual stride two for downsizing. Each cube consists of three layers. The initial layer consists of eleven convolutions with the ReLU activation function. The second layer uses Depthwise convolution to introduce non-linearity, and the third layer consists of eleven more convolutions.

Google's MobileNetv2 (CVPR 2018) was selected due to its widespread use in programs and wide usage by many papers in the literature. Papers use the framework in their research as in our investigation (Nagrath et al., 2021; Sunnetci et al., 2023; Gulzar, 1906a,b; Akarajaka et al., 2023; Hu et al., 2023). The architecture of MobileNetV2 is shown in Figure 3.

3.2.3 CNN-LSTM hybrid network

In order to explain the LSTM and understand it, we need first to examine how the Recurrent neural network (RNN) functions. Thus, the Recurrent neural network (RNN) functions by storing the output of a particular layer and feeding it back to the input to predict the layer's output. Recurrent neural networks are susceptible to the vanishing and exploding gradient problem because gradients must propagate down to

Fig. 3 The architecture of MobileNetv2 (Hu and Guo, 2021).

numerous layers of the network. Consequently, it is challenging to model the long-term dynamics (Wigington et al., 2017; Yu et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2021).

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network offers an alternative to RNN by incorporating a memory cell that encodes knowledge at each time step. Three gates specifically govern the behaviour of the cell: an input gate, a forget gate, and an output gate. These gates are used to control the amount of input data to be read (input gate I whether to forget the current cell value (forget gate f), and whether to output the new cell value (output gate k) (output gate o). These gates allow the input signal to propagate through the recurrent hidden states without affecting the output; consequently, LSTM can effectively model long-term temporal dynamics that RNNs cannot learn.

CNN has proven effective at processing image-like data by extracting discriminative features from the input images, whereas LSTM is suitable for modelling sequential data. There are two ways to combine both frameworks: unified combination and cascaded combination.

The unified combination adds a recurrent property to the conventional CNN architecture. Each image is converted into its 1D spatial sequences by concatenating the CNN features of various image regions and utilising LSTM to discover the spatial dependencies of image regions. On the other hand, the cascaded combination would process CNN and LSTM independently, with LSTM using CNN's output as input and returning sequential predictions at different timesteps. The unified combination structure has been implemented by introducing LSTM units between the CNN and the fully connected layer to improve classification accuracy.

3.2.4 Artificial neural network (ANN)

Artificial neural networks excel at complex modelling patterns and can be used for image recognition and other applications such as prediction, this is the reason that we utilised it also for the second stage to predict the AQI. Figure 4 depicts the proposed

three-layer neural network diagram. At each iteration or epoch, the neural network's learning process consists of the forward propagation of input features and the back-propagation of error. During the training phase, the weights (W as shown in Figure 4), which connect neural units in different layers, are adjusted based on the error to the input (X as depicted in Figure 4) and output (Y as illustrated in Figure 4) information of different samples (Hopfield, 1988; Jain et al., 1996). Figure 5 shows how the ANN is implemented with the use of TensorFlow.

Fig. 4 Structure of ANN.

Fig. 5 Architecture of ANN.

3.3 Second Stage: Prediction With the Use of Regression

Predictive modelling is a statistical technique that employs machine learning and data mining to predict and forecast probable outcomes using existing data that are separated per timestamp (days in our case). A forecasting model employs numerical values derived from historical data. This section provides a description of the approaches used for the second regression stage. These are the: i) ANN (it is also used in the classification stage); ii) RNN; iii) LSTM; and iv) RNN-B-LSTM; Note that the analysis of ANN is shown in the first stage section. Thus, it is not analysed in this section.

3.3.1 Recurrent Neural Network (RNN)

RNN (Sherstinsky, 2020) is a type of deep neural network in which the connections between the nodes can create a cycle, permitting the output of certain nodes to affect subsequent input to the same nodes. RNNs, which are built from feed-forward neural networks, can manage input sequences of varied lengths by utilising their internal state (memory). This enables the entity's dynamic temporal behaviour. RNNs are dynamic systems whose internal state changes at each categorization time step. This is a result of the circular connections and potential self-feedback connections between neurons in the upper and lower layers. These feedback connections allow RNNs to convey data from past occurrences to processing stages that are now occurring. Thus, RNN constructs a memory of time series.

Additionally, If RNN incorporates time delays or feedback loops, a new network or graph may be substituted for the store (Williams and Zipser, 1989). In addition to two single-layer RNNs, there are RNNs with varying degrees of connectivity. Comparable to a three-layered neural network, the Elman network¹ stores the outputs of the hidden layer within context cells. Then it is returning the context cell's output and the signal's origin to the hidden neuron. Each neuron in the hidden layer receives input from both neurons in the input layer and neurons in the context layer. Figure 6 shows how the RNN is implemented with the use of TensorFlow.

3.3.2 Long short-term memory (LSTM)

A conventional neural network cannot learn from previous iterations as the input fed to the network at one step does not pass to the next step, i.e., it does not possess memory. Whereas an RNN learns the input values from the immediately preceding iteration (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1996, 1997; Graves et al., 2008; Yu et al., 2019; Graves and Schmidhuber, 2005; Gers et al., 2002).

$X(t)$ is the input, $h(t)$, and A is the neuron to which the previous iteration's output is repeatedly fed back. Due to the addition of error gradients, the training phase of RNN results in an unstable network due to repeated updates to the neural network model's weights.

¹The Elman reference network, which is typically a two-layer network with feedback from the first layer's output to the first layer's input, can be trained using standard error backpropagation, with the output of the context cell considered an additional input.

Fig. 6 Architecture of RNN.

Using gates, the memorising process of an LSTM solves this problem. Each recurrent unit maintains a vector known as the internal cell state, which describes the information selected for retention by the preceding LSTM recurrent unit.

An LSTM is composed of four distinct gates with distinct functions, as outlined below:

1. Forget Gate(f) determines how much of the previous data can be forgotten.
2. Input Gate(I) determines how much information will be written onto the internal cell state.
3. Input modulation gate (g): which is considered as a part of the input gate. It is used to modulate the information to be written on the internal state cell from the input gate. Modulating the information held adds non-linearity, thus making it zero-mean. Zero-mean input will lead to faster convergence and thus reduce the learning time.
4. Output Gate(o): It determines the next hidden state, which is the output to be generated from the current internal cell state.

Mathematically, the LSTM can be represented as:

Forget Gate:

$$f = \sigma(W_f[h_{t-1}; x_t] + b_f) \quad (5)$$

Input Gate:

$$i = \sigma(W_i[h_{t-1}; x_t] + b_i) \quad (6)$$

Output Gate:

$$o = \sigma(W_o[h_{t-1}; x_t] + b_o) \quad (7)$$

The unique architecture of LSTM enables it to get rid of unnecessary features. The decision to remove parts of the output (by outputting a 0) is made by taking the input $X(t)$ and $h(t-1)$ at the sigmoid layer. Figure 7 shows how the RNN is implemented with the use of TensorFlow.

Fig. 7 Architecture of LSTM.

3.3.3 RNN-Bi Directional Long short-term memory Neural Network (RNN-B-LSTM)

In this section, we will show what B-LSTM is, and then we will show the RNN-B-LSTM.

Bi-Directional Long short-term memory Neural Network (B-LSTM)

In (Graves and Schmidhuber, 2005), the authors address the concept of using LSTM to analyse the past and future of a certain region. Bidirectional training provides an architectural advantage over unidirectional training for categorising phonemes. Two separate LSTM networks are connected to a single output layer and accept input in both ways. Bidirectional LSTM avoids the initial LSTM one-step truncation and calculates the complete error gradient. This method enabled the training of bidirectional LSTM with the usual Back Propagation Through Time (BPTT). Because typical RNNs only analyse each point in a sequence in one direction: backward.

RNN-B-LSTM

RNN-BLSTM is a hybrid algorithm that combines two learning algorithms: Real-Time Recurrent Learning (RTRL) training network components before cells and BPTT training network components after cells. This combination is utilised to maintain CEC

in BLSTM memory block cells that use the original formulation of B-LSTM. The latter units are compatible with RTRL since some partial derivatives (relating to the state of the cell) must be computed at each step, regardless of whether a target value is specified. Note that only the gradient of the cell is permitted to propagate through time, disconnecting the gradients of the other recurrent connections (Gers et al., 2002; Reddy and Delen, 2018).

Fig. 8 Architecture of RNN-B-LSTM.

RNN-BLSTM excels at tasks that need the long-term storage of a modest quantity of data. This attribute is the result of consuming memory blocks. Memory blocks are fitted with a forget gate that weights the information contained within the cells in such a way that, when earlier information becomes irrelevant for certain cells, the forget gate can reset the state of the individual cells inside the block. In addition to allowing for continuous prediction, forget gates can cause cells to forget their previous state, hence eliminating prediction bias. Also, memory blocks are intriguing: input and output gates prohibit superfluous data from entering or exiting the memory block. The RNN-BLSTM necessitates a particular network configuration. Since the number of memory blocks does not fluctuate dynamically, network memory is ultimately constrained. This restriction is unlikely to be overcome by uniformly increasing the network size, demonstrating that modularisation improves learning success, but it is

”not generally visible”. Figure 8 shows how the RNN-B-LSTM is implemented with the use of TensorFlow.

4 Data analysis and model training

This section provides an in-depth investigation of the data gathering, data analysis, dataset creation, features extraction, and how the classification and prediction models shown in Section 3 are trained. The image data augmentation strategies applied for the calculation of AQI are shown in Section 3.1. So, the condition for an AQI to exist is that a minimum of three pollutants should exist (SO₂, NO₂, NH₃, CO, O₃, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀), out of which one is PM.

4.1 Dataset

We used the image dataset from the VisionAir, an open-source dataset consisting of non-HDR images taken across five different locations in Delhi-Technological University, Shadipur, Punjabi Bagh, ITO, Shaheed Sukhdev College of Business Studies (Air; , 2023). The images collected are distributed as shown in Table 2. The cor-

Table 2 Image count across different locations.

Location	No. of Images
Delhi Technological University	369
Shadipur	244
Punjabi Bagh	369
Delhi Technological University	470
ITO	499
Shaheed Sukhdev College of Business Studies	1316

responding pollutant data were obtained from the Central Pollution Control Board website (Board), an online portal for monitoring the air quality across India. Using various monitoring stations for air quality in Delhi NCR, the concentrations of PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, NH₃, SO₂, O₃, temperature, and humidity were measured. The correlation between the weather parameters, temperature and humidity, and PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ were calculated.

A strong positive correlation between PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ was observed. Warm, rising air near the ground typically lifts away pollution, but when the temperature drops, the layer of warm air acts as a lid, trapping cold air at the surface. This explains the negative correlation between the temperature and the particulate pollutants by preventing the escape of the particulate pollutants.

Humidity refers to the amount of moisture in the air. The strong positive correlation between humidity and particulate pollutants explains why elevated humidity levels have a high capacity to trap pollutants, thereby increasing pollutant concentration. To determine the extent to which each pollutant contributes to the overall AQI, the correlation matrix depicted in Figure 9 was computed. From Figure 9, it can be inferred that PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and NO_x have the highest levels of correlation with the

Fig. 9 The correlation matrix between various pollutants.

AQI.

4.1.1 SMOTE algorithm

Class imbalance is a phenomenon that occurs when the distribution of classes in a dataset is unequal, i.e., the number of data points in a few classes is disproportionately large compared to other classes (as shown in Figure 13). If the problem of unbalanced data is resolved, the model’s performance will improve. Most predictions will correspond to the majority class, while minority characteristics will be treated as noise in the data and disregarded. Such a model will produce substantial bias.

An unbalanced dataset can be converted to a balanced one by resampling the data (as shown in Figure 14). In general, there are two methods to achieve that: i) Under-sampling and ii) Oversampling. Oversampling is the process of generating new data for a minority group. Therefore, it is preferred over the under-sampling techniques. Under-sampling techniques eliminate instances from the majority class, which may result in the loss of crucial data. The reason that this investigation used SMOTE approach even that there are different new (generating adversarial networks (Gonzalez-Abril et al., 2021)) and few variants (SMOTE-NC, Borderline-SMOTE, Borderline-SMOTE SVM,

Adaptive Synthetic Sampling (ADASYN) (Hu and Guo, 2021)) proposed for different scenarios similar to ours is the following:

- The SMOTE is widely used and proves its correctness (Rani et al., 2023).
- The SMOTE is also used in the latest papers (Rani et al., 2023).

The synthetic minority oversampling technique (SMOTE) is a technique that generates synthetic data for classes with fewer data samples. This algorithm assists in overcoming the issue of overfitting that occurs when random oversampling is performed. The algorithm generates new data samples and features by interpolating between instances in the feature space that is close together. SMOTE utilises the KNN algorithm to generate synthetic data. It first selects data randomly from the minority class and then determines the k-nearest neighbours from this data. Then, synthetic data is generated between the random data and the k-nearest neighbour selected at random. Figure 10 demonstrates the procedure. More specifically, in the aforesaid figure, the algorithm creates new instances of the underrepresented class/category. The green colour circles are the synthetic data generated by SMOTE, the red circle are the features belonging to the minority class, and the blue is the nearest neighbour in the feature space. This form of data augmentation for tabular data is particularly successful. SMOTE operates by picking instances that are close to one another in the feature space, drawing a line connecting the instances in the feature space, and then drawing a new instance along the line. Specifically, a minority class member is originally selected at random. Then, the case’s k nearest neighbours are identified (usually, k equals 5). A neighbour is chosen randomly, and a synthetic example is constructed between the two cases at a random location in feature space (Chawla et al., 2002).

Fig. 10 A demonstration of the SMOTE algorithm operation.

Note that in all sampling methods (especially synthetic methods such as SMOTE), we divide the data first and then apply synthetic sampling to the training data only. After training, the test set is evaluated, consisting only of original samples. The risk associated with the technique SMOTE is that the original sample is in the training set (test set), and the synthetic sample (produced from the original sample) is in the test set (training set). Thus, Figures 13 and 14 show how the training data changed over

SMOTE. The testing data are not processed over the SMOTE method (Gonzalez-Abril et al., 2021; Hu and Guo, 2021).

4.2 Features' extraction

Four image features were extracted and added to the data frame in the first stage to determine the class of the gas intensity type in the first stage and at the end by taking overall pixels to determine the AQI class (as shown in Section 3.1.1 and Figure 9). These characteristics were crucial in establishing a connection between the images and the AQI classes. The extracted features were the average RGB colour, the image contrast, the image entropy, and the ratio of pixels with high brightness, as explained below:

1. The average of red, green, and blue colour: Every image is made of pixel values in the RGB colour code, colour in the RGB colour model is described by indicating how much of each of the red, green, and blue colour intensities are present in the image. The colour is expressed as an RGB triplet (r, g, b). Each component of which can vary from zero to a maximum value of 255, assuming each colour is represented using 8 bits. As the atmosphere gets polluted, the AQI increases, and the colour of the sky changes. Hence, the average value of the red, blue, and green colour intensity present in the image is considered a feature.
2. The image contrast: - the contrast is an image's property that distinguishes objects from one another. The human sensory system is more sensitive to distinction than luminance. The image contrast is found by calculating the value of RMS Contrast using Eq. (8).,

$$\sqrt{\frac{1}{MN} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (I_{ij} - avg(I))^2} \quad (8)$$

where I_{ij} is the intensity at (i,j) pixel of the image with size $M \times N$, and $avg(I)$ is the average intensity of all pixels in the image. As AQI increases, the contrast in the image decreases.

3. The image entropy: the entropy refers to the amount of information contained in the image, which is interpreted as the average uncertainty of the information source. It is also used to quantify the texture in the image. To find the value of image entropy, Shannon entropy is used (Shannon), which visits every pixel and then compares every next surrounding pixel with the checking pixel. The formula for Shannon entropy is given by Eq. (9).

$$entropy = \sum_{i=1}^M p_i \log_2 p_i \quad (9)$$

where p_i is the probability that the pixel intensity is equal to i , and M is the maximum intensity of the image. The entropy of an image increases as AQI increases.

4. The ratio of high brightness pixels: the colour coding conversion of the utilised images is done from RGB to YCbCr, where the Y channel represents Luminance or

Brightness. Cb is the blue-difference, and Cr is the red-difference chroma element. It was noted that the brightness histogram for different AQI follows a different distribution. An image with a lower AQI (as shown in Figure 11) had a brightness histogram that was uniform compared to an image with a higher AQI (as shown in Figure 12) with a non-uniform distribution with higher concentration in the right high-brightness interval. This is demonstrated in Figures 11 and 12. Therefore, the ratio of high-brightness pixels was computed by the RGB to YCbCr colour conversion, followed by counting the number of pixels whose Y (brightness) value is larger than a set threshold (128). The ratio between the high-brightness pixels to the overall pixels in the image was then calculated. The ratio increases as the AQI increases, with a value interval of $[0,1]$.

Fig. 11 Brightness Histogram of an image with AQI 100.

In Figures 11 and 12, we demonstrate the pixel intensity in terms of frequency based on the aforementioned features extracted. Thus, each colour in the graph represents an extracted Feature.

Fig. 12 Brightness histogram of an image with AQI 220.

The imbalance in the number of data points belonging to different classes is shown in Figure 13. The SMOTE algorithm was thus used to obtain a balance in data points. Figure 14 shows the obtained balance in data points.

Note that our classification results are gathered, and based on the AQI calculation, the algorithm estimates the AQI using the following classes: good, moderate, poor, satisfactory, severe, and very poor. Figures 13 and 14 show the represented classes that resulted from our first stage classification results. Even though there are no represented classes of the good, satisfactory with the resulting classification, ML approaches know about the number of classes that we use through the model specification (at the output lines) and through the equal range split shown in Table 1. Thus, even if there are no current images with the aforementioned classes, the classifier can classify them based on the data that are related to the rest of the classes.

In the second stage, we used the same features that the first stage models used to train the prediction approach, as well as the class category that the best model predicted in the first stage and the actual AQI value calculated for the specific day (6 features and one output, which is the prediction value).

Fig. 13 Imbalance in data points.

Fig. 14 The balanced data points after using SMOTE.

4.3 The classification model training

Before training a model to classify images into their respective categories, it was necessary to manipulate the image and the resulting data frame. The images were placed in different subdirectories based on the AQI bucket/class to which they belonged. This was accomplished by matching the image’s path to its corresponding timeframe and AQI within the data frame. In addition, each subdirectory was split 80:20 between train and test data, resulting in 2321 images as a training set (where SMOTE is used) and 584 as the testing set, respectively. To convert each image to a standard size, it was rescaled to a resolution of 224×224 . In this process, the ML approach did not change the resolution of the pictures; the resolution and image size is the same. However, the standard procedure of training and validating the data from the photographs is to rescale them in memory through the training process that uses “ImageDataGenerator” and “flow_from_directory” and is called datagen. The process divides the pixel values by 255 to rescale them. It also resizes all photos to 224×224 pixels, regardless of the original size of the image in the train or validation directory. It’s also important to note that train datagen has more arguments than test datagen. This is performed in order to augment data. Data Augmentation is the technique of generating additional training data from existing training data. Existing photos are flipped, sheared, zoomed, moved, and rotated in the preceding code to increase data training and prevent overfitting (Chollet, 2016; Seetala et al., 2019). More specifically, data augmentation generates new synthetic training samples by adding small perturbations to the initial data set. The augmentation aims to render the model insensitive to such perturbations and improve its generalizability. It is also done to increase the amount of available training data. The techniques used to enhance the training set images included rotating the image by a certain angle, shifting the image’s width and height by a certain range, zooming in, applying shear, and horizontal flipping. The enhancement was performed at runtime, thereby conserving memory. All images’ pixel intensities were rescaled and normalised. Because pixel values can range from 0 to 256, each representing a colour code. Using the image as-is and passing it through a neural network makes the computation of large numbers more complicated. The values are normalised to a range of 0 to 1 to reduce the complexity.

In terms of model architecture, the CNN, CNN-LSTM hybrid network, and MobileNetV2 each had three hidden layers, and the ReLU activation function was used at the hidden layers. The output layer of six neurons was activated with a softmax activation function, which represents the probability of an input belonging to each of the six classes. Also, the dropout ratio was fixed at 0.2 and 0.5 for training cases, indicating that 20% and 50% of neurons, respectively, are activated only during the later phase of training. Since our AQI values fell into six distinct categories, a categorical cross-entropy loss function was utilised to determine the loss and precision of the model. Each epoch’s weights and other parameters were optimised using an Adam optimizer (Share, 2021) because it requires less memory and performs well with sparse data.

In addition, classification was performed using the extracted features and for an ANN. The model architecture was implemented with three layers, using the ReLU activation function in the input and hidden layers and the Adam optimiser to optimise

the weights. At the output layer, the categorical cross-entropy function was used to assign probabilities of an image belonging to each AQI class category. After training the model with the training data, the model's performance is evaluated using the testing data.

4.4 Prediction model training

After obtaining the entire set of data points on performing the SMOTE algorithm, they were split into training and testing data (i.e. a ratio of 90:10). All the features' values in the train set were scaled and normalised to reduce the computation complexity. The ANN model was trained with three layers and with the ReLU activation function to be used at the input and hidden layers. An Adam optimiser was used to optimise the weights. The LSTM model was trained with four layers with 40 units each. After training the model using the training data, the testing data is passed to the model to evaluate its performance.

4.5 Validation of the investigated ML Approaches With Cross-Validation

For our validation of the data and in order to tackle the overfitting, we use the k-fold Cross Validation technique (Stone, 1974; Allen, 1974; Pirayonesi and El-Diraby, 2019; Roberts et al., 2017; Arya, 2022) as shown in Figure 15. Thus, we validated the investigated approaches with Cross-validation. Cross-validation is a resampling technique used to assess machine learning models using a restricted data sample. A parameter named "k" specifies the number of groups a given data sample is partitioned into. Cross-validation may also be referred to as rotation estimation and/or out-of-sample testing. Cross-validation can be used to detect the overfitting of a model, showing that the model does not adequately generalise patterns and similarities in newly entered data. Cross-over validation is a technique for testing machine learning models in which multiple models are trained on separate sections of input data. In K-fold cross-validation, a data set is split into K folds, and the model's performance is evaluated on additional data. K indicates the number of groups into which the sample data is divided. For example, if the k value is 5, we can refer to it as 5-fold cross-validation. Each fold acts as a test sample at some point in the process. To perform cross-validation, the cross-validation workflow usually includes the following steps:

1. Select your k-value.
2. Divide the data set into the specified number of folds.
3. First, use the k-1 fold as the test data set and the remaining folds as the training data set.
4. Validate the model with the test dataset after training it with the training dataset.
5. Save the result for validation.
6. Change the value of the test data set k and repeat steps 3 to 5.

Therefore, we chose k-1 as the test data set for the first round and k-2 as the test data set for the following round. By the end, you would have validated the model on

every fold you have. In the end, average the results produced in step 5 to summarise the model's skill.

Fig. 15 K-Fold Cross Validation technique

5 Performance evaluation

This section provides the metrics used in the two stages, performance evaluation of the investigated ML approaches related to the classification and prediction process, as shown in Section 3.

5.1 Metrics Used

This section provides the different metrics used for each stage (Harikrishnan, 2019).

5.1.1 First Stage Classification Metrics

The following metrics are used in the evaluation of the classification approaches $F1$ Score, *Precision* (P), *Recall* (R) or *True Positive Rate* (TPR), *False Positive Rate* (FPR), and *False Negative Rate* (FNR) based on the confusion matrix evaluation (Liang, 2022). We first describe the confusion matrix and its associated metrics to comprehend how we calculated the aforementioned metrics. Thus, the *Confusion Matrix* is a tabular representation of findings that can be used to validate the performance of ML models that have been trained. Regarding a binary classification problem, the alternative outcomes in relation to the anticipated outcome can be classified as follows:

- True Positives (TP): Classified Positive (Yes) and correctly classified. TP is the number of data samples with attacks detected correctly.
- True Negatives (TN): Classified Negative (No) and correctly classified. TN is the number of benign samples detected correctly.
- False Positives (FP): Classified Positive (Yes) and wrongly classified. FP is the number of data samples with false attack detection.
- False Negatives (FN): Classified Negative (No) and wrongly classified. FN is the number of attack samples missed.

According to the definitions of TP, TN, FP, FN, we can compute the following metrics: *Precision* (P) = $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$, *Recall* (R) = $1 - FNR$, *F1 Score* = $\frac{2 \cdot P \cdot R}{P+R}$ where $FNR = \frac{FN}{TP+FN}$, and $FPR = \frac{FP}{FP+TN}$. Note that *Recall* can also be given by $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$.

5.1.2 Second Stage Regression Metrics

The following metrics are used in the evaluation of the regression approaches *Mean Squared Error (MSE)*, *Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)*, *Mean Absolute Error (MAE)*, *Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)* and *Accuracy* (Overview, 2023). The explanation of each metric is shown in the following section:

- The MSE is the average squared difference between the estimated/predicted values and the actual values. It is calculated with the following formula $MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2$. Where the \hat{Y}_i is the prediction value, and the Y_i is the real value. MSE is a risk function corresponding to the expected value of the squared error loss. In MSE, the outliers are punished severely. However, the error is not in the original units of the time series, making it more difficult to read. Since the error is scale dependent, it cannot be compared to other time series models that use different units.
- The RMSE is the root of the average squared difference between the estimated/predicted values and the actual values. It is calculated with the following formula $RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2}$. Where the \hat{Y}_i is the prediction value, and the Y_i is the real value. RMSE continues to penalise outliers severely. Also, the time series will have errors in its original units, and it is similar to the best of both MSE and MAE. However, it is less interpretable because you continue to square the faults, and it is scale dependent, so incomparable to other time series models employing various units.
- The MAE is a measure of the differences in error between paired observations of the same occurrence; thus is the mean of the absolute value of the differences between the estimated/predicted values and the actual values. MAE is computed by dividing the sum of absolute errors by the sample size. It is calculated with the following formula $MAE = (\frac{1}{n}) \sum_{i=1}^n |Y_i - \hat{Y}_i|$. Where the \hat{Y}_i is the prediction value, and the Y_i is the real value. The MAE is easy to understand; it reflects the data and the projected units that are inaccurate. However, it doesn't penalise outliers; it is scale dependent and incomparable to other time series models employing various units.

- The MAPE is the average or mean of absolute percentage errors associated with projections. For the purpose of computing MAPE, percentage errors are added without regard to sign. This metric is simple because the error is presented as a percentage; the error is the divergence between the observed or real value and the projected value. Additionally, when using absolute percentage errors, the issue of positive and negative errors cancelling each other out is eliminated. MAPE has managerial appeal and is hence a popular forecasting metric. The MAPE decreases as forecasts get more accurate. It is calculated with the following formula $MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{A_t - F_t}{A_t} \right| \%$. Where the \hat{Y}_i is the prediction value, and the Y_i is the real value. MAE is easy to understand and scale independently; hence it is possible to compare many time series. However, If the real value is close to zero or zero, there is an infinite error, and also, lower forecasts are limited to a 100% mistake rate, whereas higher forecasts might have an infinite error rate; therefore, it is biased to under-predict.
- The introduced Accuracy (ACC) by us, is a metric that reflects how accurate the approach is in terms of percentage. It is calculated with the following formula $ACC = 1 - MAPE = 1 - \frac{100}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{A_t - F_t}{A_t} \right| \%$. Where the \hat{Y}_i is the prediction value, and the Y_i is the real value. ACC is simple to comprehend and scale independently, allowing for the comparison of numerous time series. However, if the actual value is close to zero or zero, there is an infinite error. Smaller forecasts are limited to a 100 % error rate, whereas larger forecasts may have an infinite error rate; hence, it is biased to underestimate.

5.2 Classification

In the classification phase (first phase), we used 75% of the existing data for training and 25% for testing. Our examination of the testing data showed that the accuracies of the proposed models are kept steady with a difference of $+ - 0, 10\%$. We validated the data using the test percentage of the data.

After the training and testing the resulting accuracy of the classification models is shown in Table 3. More precisely, the MobileNetV2 achieved an accuracy of 75.63% with five epochs, the CNN-LSTM achieved 85% with only ten epochs, the CNN achieved an accuracy of 85.05% with twenty epochs, and at last, ANN achieved 99.14% with 100 epochs. Overall, the approach with the best accuracy is the ANN, but the approach with the least number of training epochs with higher accuracy is the CNN-LSTM. Thus, according to Table 3, the number of epochs needed for a model to achieve its highest accuracy. Each approach resulted in a different number of epochs. The most accurate approach, which is the ANN, needed 100 epochs, but CNN-LSTM, which is the second in accuracy, needed only 20 in order to conclude and achieve the highest accuracy. For the rest of the approaches, the MobileNetV2 is trained using 5 epochs, while the CNN is trained using 40 epochs. Note that, in order to conclude with epochs, we examine each approach with a different epoch using brute force investigation, and we examine the resulting accuracy; our target is to achieve the highest accuracy note also that the CNN model was trained under two dropout ratio conditions of 0.2 and 0.5. The confusion matrix obtained on passing the testing data to the ANN

model is demonstrated in Figure 16. The images are classified into classes of values (Good:0-50, Satisfactory:51-100, Moderate:101-200, Poor:201-300, Very Poor:301-400, Severe:>401).

Table 3 Classification: the resulting accuracy, precision, recall and F1-Score

Architecture	No. of epochs	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
CNN	40	85.05%	89.69 %	80.14 %	84.64 %
MobileNetV2	5	75.63%	78.36 %	74.87 %	76.57 %
CNN-LSTM	20	85%	88.69 %	80.14 %	84.19 %
ANN	100	99.14%	99.92 %	98.89 %	99.40 %

Fig. 16 The classification confusion matrix of ANN.

In Figure 17, we show how each epoch improves the ACC in classifying the investigated approaches.

5.3 Prediction

In the prediction phase (second phase), we used 90% of the existing data for training and 10% for testing. Our examination of the testing data showed that the accuracies of the proposed models are kept steady with a difference of $\pm 0,10\%$. We validated the data using the test percentage of the data. After the training and testing, the resulting accuracy of the classification models is shown in Table 4.

Fig. 17 ACC Vs Iterations Vs Approaches.

More specifically, after the test images are classified by the best approach (ANN) in the first phase. Then, in the second phase, the examination utilises the ANN, RNN, LSTM, and RNN-B-LSTM models to evaluate their performance using the dataset generated according to the features identified in Section 4.2. The results of the prediction models are shown in Table 4. According to Table 4, the approach with the highest accuracy is the RNN-B-LSTM with an accuracy of 98.73%. The LSTM follows with an accuracy of 93.6%, next the ANN follows with an accuracy of 86.9%, and lastly, the RNN follows with an accuracy of 73.45%. Additionally, in the case of "Loss during training", the approaches ANN, RNN, LSTM, and RNN-B-LSTM were observed to be approximately 0.1312, 0.0399, 0.0202, 0.0213, respectively, in the presence of synthetic data generated by the SMOTE algorithm, respectively.

During our simulations, we also measure the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). Thus, in the case of RMSE, the value of the approaches ANN, RNN, LSTM, and RNN-B-LSTM were observed to be approximately 0.41, 0.23, 0.21, 0.09 and 0.37, 0.19, 0.14, 0.02 respectively in the absence and presence of synthetic data generated by the SMOTE algorithm, respectively.

In Figure 18, we show how each epoch improves the MSE in predicting the investigated approaches over iteration. Furthermore, Table 5 demonstrates examples of actual versus predicted AQI using the RNN-B-LSTM model.

Table 4 Prediction of our models' accuracy

Architecture	Loss during training	Mean Square Error (MSE)	Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)	Accuracy (1-MAPE)	SMOTE at Training Data?
ANN	0.1312	0.1428	21.2965	0.131	86.9%	YES
LSTM	0.0202	0.0202	11.2820	0.064	93.6%	YES
RNN-B-LSTM	0.0213	0.00054750	2.2688	0.0126	98.73%	YES
RNN	0.0399	0.0399	17.7637	0.0923	73.45%	YES

Fig. 18 MSE Vs Iterations Vs Approaches.

A comparison of the actual value versus the AQI value predicted by the model is shown in Figure 19 and Table 5. More specifically, we examine the prediction of the actual AQI vs predicted AQI where the predicted AQI was taken from the RNN-B-LSTM with SMOTE in the current architecture. In our examination, we value from 0 to 400, and the model is performing with high accuracy because the training set included samples from all the range of the values of AQI.

Fig. 19 Actual versus predicted value using RNN-B-LSTM model.

Note that in previous experimentation, we examine the direct evaluation of AQI from the ANN and then prediction using RNN-B-LSTM with a small change in the

Table 5 Actual versus predicted AQI (From RNN-B-LSTM) on test images/data

Actual AQI	Predicted AQI From RNN-B-LSTM	Error
0	1.04	1.04
40.06	41.12	1.06
69	70.13	1.13
90	90.75	0.75
102	103.25	1.25
133	131.85	1.15
271	272.13	1.13
331	331.6	0.6
401	399.35	0.65

current architecture. In the architecture, the classification phase is changed to do regression than classification with the ANN and extracting the value of the AQI based on the pictures. Then we used the AQI regression value and trained the RNN-B-LSTM to predict the future AQI. However, the accuracy of the ANN (which was the highest in this investigation) approach was as low as 83%. This is the reason we used classification in order to improve the accuracy of prediction. Please note that we tackle the overfitting/underfitting issue using the SMOTE algorithm (Ke et al., 2023) and validate it with a k-fold investigation. Thus, the oversampling technique (SMOTE) is one of the investigation focus. In terms of validation, in our examinations, the mean score of the K-Fold was around the accuracy (+-5%) of each approach. This shows that our investigation approaches are validated correctly, and the examination is correct. In this investigation, we test the applicability of our approach to identifying the categories that the data are where missing (as shown in Section 4.2); as we show in Table 5, our approach had classified all the categories successfully and predicted the AQI accurately (especially the categories good and satisfactory) More precisely, we classify pictures associated with AQI that represented all categories (9 images), with this examination, we show the applicability of our approach.

6 Conclusions and future work

This section contains the results drawn from the paper’s investigation as well as recommendations for future research related to our investigation.

6.1 Conclusion

We investigated and implemented methods for classifying and predicting AQI values from images, then compared and analysed the performance of the models. In the first stage, the CNN, MobileNetV2, CNN-LSTM hybrid, and ANN Deep ML models were fed images to classify them according to their AQI category. The ANN model provided the highest level of accuracy, 99.14%. Then, in the second stage, ANN, LSTM, RNN-B-LSTM, and RNN DEEP ML models (neural networks) were implemented to predict the AQI value. In the first stage, synthetic data were generated using SMOTE to create an equal number of data points belonging to each AQI category. After generating

synthetic data, the ANN and, in the end, the RNN-B-LSTM model achieved a 98.73% accuracy rate. For the realisation and the correct implementation of our investigation, an application was created using Tkinter, and a GUI was formed comprising the ANN classification model and the RNN-B-LSTM prediction model.

6.2 Future work

In our future work, we plan to test additional classification and prediction models and incorporate additional weather characteristics, such as wind direction and air pressure, to improve the performance of our method. In addition, we will continue to collect more images from various regions of the globe and expand the dataset to make the models less region-specific. Moreover, we will examine the performance of our proposed image-based classification and prediction AI/ML approach in differentiating between fog and smog (polluted air) in future work. [Finally, building upon the insights gained from our study in Delhi, our future research endeavors will expand to include diverse urban environments, specifically Nicosia, Cyprus, and Amman, Jordan. These cities, with their distinct geographical and climatic conditions, offer a contrasting backdrop to the urban landscape of Delhi. Nicosia, with its smaller urban scale and different industrial profile, presents a unique set of environmental variables, while Athens's coastal Mediterranean setting introduces different atmospheric dynamics impacting air quality. The extension of our research to these cities will enable us to test the adaptability and scalability of our AI models in varied urban settings. This comparative analysis aims to refine our models further, enhancing their predictive accuracy and applicability across different global contexts. Ultimately, this future work will contribute significantly to the development of tailored, location-specific strategies for air quality monitoring and management, providing a comprehensive framework that can be adapted to various urban environments worldwide.](#)

Acknowledgments. This research is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N^o739578 and the government of the Republic of Cyprus through the Directorate General for European Programmes, Coordination and Development.

Declarations

Funding

This research is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N^o739578 and the government of the Republic of Cyprus through the Directorate General for European Programmes, Coordination and Development. This work has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement No 101087257. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This work has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement No 101095363. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the

European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Conflicts of interest/Competing interests

There is no potential competing interest

Ethics approval

Not applicable

Consent for publication

All authors consent for publication

Availability of data and materials

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request after the publication of the article.

Code availability

The code implemented during the current study is available from the corresponding author on reasonable request after the publication of the article.

Authors' contributions

All authors are equally contribute in the realisation of this study

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